

Thermodynamics of the Interaction of Transition Metal Ions with Diphenic Acid

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The thermodynamic functions of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Pd(II) complexes with diphenic acid have been determined in a medium of 0.1M NaClO₄. The analysis of results shows the Cu(II) and Pd(II) complexes to be square planer and Mn(II), Co(II) and Ni(II) as octahedra.

THE metal complexes of diphenic acid have been studied in relation of their preparation, chemical analysis and their separation^{1,2}. Recently the studies have also been carried out on the stability of diphenic acid complexes with some less familiar elements, viz. Ce(IV), Th(IV), etc.³. In this paper are presented the thermodynamic data of chelation of bivalent transition metal ions with diphenic acid in 50% water-dioxane and 0.1 M NaClO₄ medium, which corresponds to the net reaction, represented by

Materials and Methods :

Metal chlorides, diphenic acid, dioxane, sodium perchlorate, perchloric acid, sodium hydroxide all were of (BDH) AR grade. All the solutions were prepared in 50% water-dioxane. The experimental procedure for the determination of constants was similar to that described earlier⁴. The correction of pH and of volumes were made according to the method reported in the literature^{5,6}. It was confirmed that with the high ligand metal ratios 5 : 1 used in our studies, the formation of the polynuclear and the hydroxocomplexes could be neglected.

Calculations :

The following sets of titrations were performed against 0.1 M NaOH at 30±0.1° and 40±0.1° for finding out the value of pK_{a1} and pK_{a2} of diphenic acid.

- A-10 ml solvent + 10 ml. HClO₄ (0.01 M)
- B-20 ml diphenic acid + 10 ml HClO₄ (0.01 M)

From the titration curves, the average no. of protons \bar{n}_H were calculated using the relation (2) of Irving and Rossotti⁷.

$$\bar{n}_H = Y - \frac{(V'' - V')(N_0 + E_0)}{(V^0 + V^1)T_L^0} \quad \dots (2)$$

where the terms have their usual significance. The formation curves of the proton complexes were obtained by plotting \bar{n}_H against pH. The pK values at two temperatures are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF DIPHENIC ACID IN 0.1M NaClO₄ AT 30° AND 40°

Temp °C	pK _{a1}	pK _{a2}
30	3.80	6.69
40	3.75	6.48

Formation curves for finding out the stability constants of metal complexes were constructed from the values of \bar{n} and $-\log R^{2-}$, which were calculated from the well known relations used by Sharma et al⁸.

In the case of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Pd(II) the precipitation during potentiometric titrations precluded determinations of \bar{n} values >1.6 >1.8 >1.7 >2.1 and >2.4 respectively. The logK values reported here are accurate to ±0.03 log units and the values of ΔH and ΔS are reliable to ±0.5 K cal mole⁻¹ and ±2.0 cal mole⁻¹ deg⁻¹ respectively.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 gives the dissociation constants of diphenic acid at 30° and 40°, and Table 2 summarizes the values of the formation constants. The values of enthalpies and entropies corresponding to the first step reaction and second step reaction are given in Table 3. The value of pK_{a2} is in good agreement with the value reported in the literature², while the value of pK_{a1} was found to be 3.80 instead of 4.32 (literature value). This may be due to the difference in solvents used, ionic strength or the temperature. The difference between the successive formation constants at 30° is much smaller for the Pd(II) complex (log K₁/K₂=0.76) as compared to

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TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF METAL COMPLEXES OF DIPHENIC ACID IN 0.1M NaClO₄ AT 30° AND 40°

Transition ion	Metal	Temp °C	Formation constants		
			log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂
3d ⁴	Mn(II)	30	5.74	2.18	7.92
		40	5.54	2.00	7.54
3d ⁷	Co(II)	30	5.88	2.39	8.27
		40	5.65	2.17	7.82
3d ⁸	Ni(II)	30	7.25	3.85	11.10
		40	7.00	3.59	10.59
3d ⁹	Cu(II)	30	7.51	3.76	11.27
		40	7.24	3.66	10.90
3d ¹⁰	Pd(II)	30	7.00	6.24	13.24
		40	6.52	5.52	12.04

may be explained on account of unique electronic configuration d⁹ of the Cu(II) ion, which is subject to Jahn-Teller distortion. The effect of this would bring a more effective neutralisation of cationic and anionic charges by reducing the distance between metal and donor atoms and hence would also diminish the order influence of residual metal ion field on water dipoles. This would lead to an additional gain of entropy. The large difference in entropy of formation of Pd(II) complex and other metal complexes results partly from the unusually high entropy of aqueous Pd(II)¹⁰. It also seems likely that the greater exothermicity is caused by the formation of π bonds Izatt et al¹⁰ point out that the entropies of hydration of Pd(II) (g) indicate that the Pd(II) ion has less solvent ordering effect.

TABLE 3—STEPWISE ΔF° AND ΔH° VALUES (IN K CALS MOLE⁻¹) AND ΔS° VALUES IN GIBBS MOLE⁻¹ (CAL MOLE⁻¹ DEG⁻¹) AT 30° FOR THE REACTION—

Thermodynamic Parameter	[M(H ₂ O) ₆] ²⁺ + nR ⇌ [M(H ₂ O) _{6-x} R _n] ²⁻²ⁿ + 2nH ⁺ + xH ₂ O in 0.1M NaClO ₄					
	nR	Mn(II)	Co(II)	Ni(II)	Cu(II)	Pd(II)
-ΔF°	1 diphenic acid	7.96	8.15	10.05	10.41	9.70
	2 diphenic acid	2.12	3.42	5.51	5.24	8.94
-ΔH°	1 diphenic acid	8.32	9.57	10.40	11.23	19.97
	2 diphenic acid	7.49	9.15	10.81	6.24	29.95
ΔS°	1 diphenic acid	- 1.19	-4.67	- 1.47	-2.70	-33.87
	2 diphenic acid	-17.70	-18.91	-17.50	-3.30	-69.35

the other metal complexes for which the value of log K₁/K₂ ≈ 3.50, this indicates that the formation of 1 : 2 complex of Pd(II) with diphenic acid takes place with greater ease than corresponding complexes with other metals.

The values of -ΔH° for the first step reaction increases from Mn(II) to Cu(II) following a small change, while it is sufficiently higher in the case of Pd(II). This may be due to the greater ligand field stabilisation energy and greater polarisation effect of Pd(II). The values of -ΔF° (Table 3) also indicate that the formation of 1 : 2 complex of Pd(II) is comparatively easier. Table 3 also gives the values of entropies for stepwise reaction of Mn(II), Co(II) and Ni(II) ions with diphenic acid. It is known that these metal ions in solutions exist as octahedrally hydrated⁹, we therefore assign an octahedral structure for the complexes of these metals. The decrease in entropy for the second step reaction in each case may be attributed to statistical effects.

The values of ΔS° show that with the exception of Cu(II) ion, where ΔS° values are comparatively much higher, the values of ΔS° for Co(II), Ni(II), Mn(II) and Pd(II) are much lower, these results

References

1. V. I. AGATONOVA and I. P. PYAZANOB, *Chem. Abs.*, 1968, 68, 119027b.
2. V. I. AGATONOVA and I. P. PYAZANOB, *Chem. Abs.*, 1970, 72, 96256y
3. C. L. SHARMA and P. K. JAIN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, 15(A), 1110
4. W. U. MALIK, C. L. SHARMA, M. C. JAIN and Y. ASHRAF, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1971, 33, 4339.
5. R. M. SATHE, N. MAHADEVAN and S. Y. SHETTY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 1166.
6. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2910.
7. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
8. V. S. SHARMA, H. B. MATHUR and P. S. KULKARNI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, 3, 146.
9. P. GEORGE and D. S. MECLURE, *Progress in Inorganic Chemistry Vol. I*, Interscience, New York, 1959 (Edited by F. A. Cotton).
10. R. M. IZATT, G. D. WATT, D. EATOUGH and J. J. CHRISTENSEN, *J. Chem. Soc. A.*, 1967, 1304.